

ISic0821

Fragment of a Latin inscription relating to building works

Language

Latin

Type

building

Material

marble

Object

tablet

Editor

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Catina

Place of origin (modern)

Catania

Provenance

found in via Dusmet, in the drain under the city market, in 1958

Coordinates

37.5014343, 15.0890466

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Catania, In storage, Ex Manifattura Tabacchi - Catania, Via Garibaldi, 233 , Soprintendenza di Catania

Physical Description

Fragment of a marble slab, broken on all four sides

Dimensions

Height 16 cm

Width 32 cm

Depth 6.5 cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. [- - -]qui c[- - -]
2. [- - -]e]x eodem rigor[e - - -]
3. [- - -]ma parte ex quo pila ++ [- - -]
4. [- - -]odum tutā[m a]dq(ue) adeo cum et +[- - -]
5. [- - -]molem istam [n]avigis adpulsis sca[- - -]
6. [- - -]ndis suscipiendis oneribus consecu[- - -]
7. [- - -]CCC [n(ummos)] meatibus urbicis maḡno prae[- - -]
8. [- - -]tionis a[- - -]

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

The fragment, discovered in 1958 is commonly associated with the fragmentary

letter of Julius Paternus (ISic0308), and two further fragments (ISic1664 and ISic3153). Although all show similarities, and all appear to relate to expenditure in relation to construction works, there are mild differences in palaeography between ISic0308 and the others, and the fragments all have different thicknesses. It remains therefore an open question as to precisely what the relationship between the various fragments might be, if any. This fragment has not been directly restudied since its original publication by Manganaro in 1959.

Digital identifiers:

TM 699462

Bibliography

1888-. L'année épigraphique: revue des publications épigraphiques relatives a l'antiquité romaine.. *L'année épigraphique : revue des publications épigraphiques relatives a l'antiquité romaine..* At 1960.0202

Manganaro, G. 1959. Epigrafi frammentarie di Catania. *Kokalos*. 5: 145-158. At 156-158 no.B fig.3

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